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T2.2: Analysis of yield stability under climate stress in the BOPACT field trial in Belgium

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Abstract

Crop yield and yield stability are important indicators of agricultural productivity, especially in the face of climate change and global food demand. Yield stability refers to a crop's ability to produce consistent yields over time. This study investigated the impact of management practices—including slurry type, compost application, and tillage method—on yield stability within the BOPACT multi-year field trial. The coefficient of variation (CV) which offers a relative measure that allows for comparison across different management practices (treatments) was used to assess the yield stability of the main crops. By employing this method, we aimed to identify the most stable and reliable treatments and experimental factors for long-term stable agricultural production under climate extremes. The analysis revealed that climatic conditions, particularly drought and extreme rainfall, significantly influenced both yield and yield stability of maize and spring barley (crops that were planted during years that climatic extremes were identified). However, no significant effects of the tested treatments / factors, or their interactions on yield stability were detected. These findings suggest that while management practices may enhance yield under optimal conditions, soil quality and other factors may play a more significant role in yield stability. This preliminary study underscores the importance of adapting agricultural practices to changing climatic conditions, while recognizing the need for further long-term research to better understand the complex interactions between management practices, environmental factors, soil, and yield stability.

Introduction

Crop yield is one of the most fundamental indicators of agricultural productivity and efficiency. High yields are essential for meeting the growing global demand for food, especially as the population increases and agricultural land becomes more limited. However, it is not just the level of yield that matters—yield stability is equally crucial.

Yield stability refers to a crop's ability to produce reliable yields across different environments and over multiple growing seasons. In modern agriculture, achieving both high and stable yields is a key objective. In the context of climate change, where extreme weather events like droughts, floods, or heat waves are becoming more frequent, consistent crop performance is critical for ensuring global food security. This consistency allows farmers to plan more effectively, reduces volatility in food prices, and supports long-term sustainability in food production. By understanding yield stability, farmers and breeders can select management practices and crop varieties that are both productive and reliable across diverse conditions (FAO, 2002).

Estimating yield stability involves analysing how consistently a crop type produces similar yields across different environments, locations, or over time (such as in long-term field trials). To quantify yield stability, statistical methods are commonly employed, using yield stability indexes (Döring & Reckling, 2018; Reckling et al., 2021), focusing on the variation in yields and the relationship between yield and environmental factors. Each method has its strengths and limitations, and the choice of approach often depends on the nature of the trial data and the specific objectives of the study (Reckling et al., 2021). Combining multiple methods can provide a more comprehensive understanding of yield stability.

In this study we aimed to investigate if the management practices in the BOPACT long-term field experiment and more specifically the type of slurry, the compost application and the tillage method affect the yield stability and identify management practices that lead to stable yields even under climatic extremes.

Methodology

Description of the BOPACT field trial

BOPACT is a multi-year field trial, initiated in 2010 at the Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO) in Belgium, to explore the following objectives (D'Hose et al., 2016):

- **SOM maintenance and enhancement:** To assess whether soil organic matter (SOM) can be maintained or increased under the legal constraints of the Nitrates Directive, using cattle or pig slurry combined with good agricultural practices such as cover cropping and straw incorporation. If SOM cannot be maintained, the trial investigates whether adding an annual dose of compost can achieve this goal without increasing the risk of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) leaching.
- **Impact of slurry type, tillage, and compost on soil quality:** To evaluate the effects of different slurry types, non-inversion tillage, and repeated plant-based farm compost applications on soil's chemical, physical, and biological quality. This also includes assessing impacts on crop production and quality, nutrient losses, and the soil's ability to suppress diseases.

The field trial is located in Merelbeke, Belgium (50.9853 N, 3.7737 E) at an elevation of 24 meters above sea level. The climate is temperate and fully humid, with warm summers, an average annual precipitation of 725 mm, and a mean annual temperature of 9°C (KMI meteorological station, Melle). The soil is classified as a **Bathygleyic Cambisol** (Dondeyne et al., 2014) with a sandy loam texture in the Ap horizon (0–35 cm), consisting of 57.0% sand, 37.7% silt, and 5.3% clay (USDA classification).

The experiment uses a **strip-split plot design** (split-block) (Figure 1) with plot dimensions of 15 x 11 m, incorporating three experimental factors with four replications:

1. **Slurry type** (horizontal factor): cattle vs. pig slurry
2. **Tillage practice** (vertical factor): conventional tillage vs. non-inversion tillage
3. **Plant based farm compost application** (subplot factor): 0 vs. 2000 kg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹

The trial follows a 4-year crop rotation (Figure 2), including forage maize (*Zea mays*), potato (*Solanum tuberosum*), spring barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), and fodder beet (with leek (*Allium porrum*)) during the first rotation in 2013). Cover crops, such as winter rye (*Hordeum vulgare*), white mustard (*Sinapis alba*), and Italian ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum*), are sown in autumn depending on timing and conditions (Table 1). The spring barley straw is incorporated into the soil (0–5 cm) using a rotary cultivator.

Figure 1: Experimental design in the BOPACT field trial

Both pig slurry (PS) and cattle slurry (CS) are applied at a rate of 170 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ approximately one week before sowing or planting the crops in spring. The slurry is surface-applied using a slurry injector, followed by immediate incorporation into the soil (0–10 cm) using a cultivator. A few days later, the soil is tilled to a depth of 25–30 cm, either with a conventional plough for the conventionally tilled plots (P) or with an Actisol cultivator for the non-inversion tillage plots (NIT).

To ensure all treatments meet crop nutrient requirements, mineral fertilizers are applied in addition to the slurry, ensuring that all plots receive an equal amount of nitrogen (N). Following this, seedbeds are prepared using a rolling harrow.

Plots also receive either 0 or 2000 kg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ of farm compost (C), prepared at ILVO (Steel et al., 2012) designated as C0 (no compost) and C1 (compost) plots. The compost is applied after harvest in the fall and incorporated into the topsoil (0–5 cm) using a rolling harrow.

Figure 2: Crop rotation in the BOPACT field trial

Table 1: Sowing and harvesting details for the main crops

Year	Main crop	Sowing Date	Harvest date	Growing season (days)
2010	Silage maize	06/05/2010	13/10/2010	160
2011	Potato	19/04/2011	07/09/2011	141
2012	Spring barley	04/04/2012	12/08/2012	130
2013	Leek	08/07/2013	25/11/2013	140
2014	Silage maize	30/04/2014	23/09/2014	146
2015	Potato	24/04/2015	18/08/2015	116
2016	Spring barley	21/04/2016	16/08/2016	117
2017	Fodder beet	12/04/2017	25/10/2017	196
2018	Silage maize	09/05/2018	21/09/2018	135
2019	Potato	18/04/2019	05/09/2019	140
2020	Spring barley	07/04/2020	06/08/2020	121
2021	Fodder beet	23/04/2021	22/10/2021	182
2022	Silage maize	29/04/2022	05/09/2022	129
2023	Potato	26/05/2023	28/08/2023	94

Crop yield determination

Crop yields have been measured annually since 2010. Forage maize is harvested when the whole plant reaches a dry matter content of approximately 30%. Two rows, 10 meters long (15 m²), from the middle of each plot are harvested using a Haldrup M-63 maize harvester, and a sample is taken for drying. Potatoes are harvested around September, with two rows of 8 meters (12 m²) harvested manually from the centre of each plot. The harvested potatoes are weighed, and a random sample of tubers is selected, and dried.

Spring barley is harvested when the grain reaches a dry matter content of about 85%. Two strips of approximately 20 m² from each plot are harvested using a plot combine harvester. The grain is weighed, and a sample of about 1 kg is collected for drying. Leek is harvested in November, with four rows of 4 meters (12 m²) manually harvested from each plot. A random choice of leek plants is washed, cut into pieces, and dried.

Yields for forage maize, potato tubers, spring barley grain, and leek are reported on a dry weight basis. Fresh plant samples are dried for 48 hours at 70°C to determine dry matter yield.

Yield stability index

The Coefficient of Variation (CV) normalizes the absolute variability of yield data (i.e., standard deviation (SD)) relative to the mean yield, so the CV is defined as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean. Because it is independent of the unit in which the measurement was taken, it can be used to compare data sets with different units or widely different means. As a percentage (Equation 1), CV allows for direct comparisons of variability across trials with different mean yields, providing a more standardized measure of stability. A high CV indicates that the group is more variable, whereas a low value would suggest the opposite thus, a lower CV indicates greater yield stability, which is desirable in agricultural systems where consistency is key.

$$CV = \left(\frac{\sigma}{\mu}\right) \cdot 100 \quad \text{where:} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

- σ is the **standard deviation** of the data set.
- μ is the **mean** of the data set.
- The result is multiplied by 100 to express the CV as a percentage.

Climate extremes

To identify climate extremes during the growing seasons of the various crops, degree days and cumulative rainfall were estimated. These calculations were tailored to each crop's specific growing season and climatic requirements. The degree days quantify the accumulation of heat or cold over time, which influences the growth and development of crops, while cumulative rainfall was measured to assess water availability during critical growth periods.

Daily climate data were sourced from the AGRI4CAST dataset provided by the Joint Research Centre (JRC). This dataset includes historical meteorological data from 1979 onwards. To capture climate extremes, the 10th and 90th percentiles of the indicators were calculated. These percentiles were used as thresholds to define extreme conditions:

- Extreme cold or insufficient heat: Defined by daily degree day values falling below the 10th percentile.
- Extreme heat: Defined by daily degree day values exceeding the 90th percentile.
- Drought extremes: Defined by cumulative rainfall values below the 10th percentile.
- Rainfall extremes: Defined by cumulative rainfall values above the 90th percentile.

These percentile thresholds were calculated separately for each crop's growing requirements and sensitive growing periods (e.g., for maize the flowering and kernel development stages are sensitive to water availability).

Results

Previous results for the BOPACT field trial identified that both the repeated application of compost and non-inversion tillage improved chemical, physical and biological soil quality whereby the positive effects of non-inversion tillage were situated in the topsoil (0–10 cm). Nevertheless, the effects on crop yield and disease suppression were not conclusive (D'Hose et al., 2016). In this study, the yield and yield stability were evaluated both per treatment and per experimental factor category (slurry type, tillage management, compost application) to identify potential agroecological (AE) practices that show highest yield stability in years of climatic stress such as drought and heat.

Analysis per treatment

Yield

In Figure 3, the mean annual dry matter (DM) yields of the different main crops in the rotation are presented per year and per treatment (combination of factors). In Figure 4 the mean DM yields per crop and per treatment are shown across years. It is observed that there are statistically significant differences among the years for all crops but not among treatments apart from the spring barley DM yield ($p < 0.001$) and the fodder beet which approached significance ($p = 0.08$) (Table 2). A post hoc analysis for Spring barley indicated that yield is statistically higher ($p < 0.001$) in treatments that receive cattle slurry combined with non-inversion tillage instead of pig slurry combine with conventional ploughing. The combination of cattle slurry combined with conventional ploughing and addition of compost is leads to statistically significant yield differences compared to the similar combination but with addition of pig slurry.

Figure 3: Mean annual yield per year and per treatments for each crop. The treatments are combination of the following factors: CS: cattle slurry; PS: pig slurry; NIT: non-inversion tillage; P: conventional tillage; C0: no compost application; C1: application of 2000 kg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ plant-based farm compost;

Figure 4: Mean annual yield per treatment across years for each crop. The treatments are combination of the following factors: CS: cattle slurry; PS: pig slurry; NIT: non-inversion tillage; P: conventional tillage; C0: no compost application; C1: application of 2000 kg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ plant-based farm compost;

Table 2: Analysis of Variance results for response variable: Yield

		F	Df	Pr(>F)
Silage maize	Treatment	0.40	7	0.90
	Year	92.52	1	<0.001
Potato	Treatment	0.70	7	0.67
	Year	26.47	1	<0.001
Spring barley	Treatment	7.72	7	<0.001
	Year	119.52	1	<0.001
Fodder beet	Treatment	1.96	7	0.08
	Year	239.67	1	<0.001

Yield stability

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to evaluate the effects of treatment and year on yield stability, measured by the CV for the four main crops. Figure 5 presents the CV for each crop in the rotation by year and treatment. The ANOVA results (Table 3) indicate that the **year** had a significant impact on the CV for silage maize

($p = 0.02$) and spring barley ($p = 0.03$). Although treatment effects were not significant for any of the crops studied, a marginal significance was observed for potato ($p = 0.05$). Additionally, neither treatment nor year exhibited significant effects on fodder beet.

Figure 5: Coefficient of variation (CV) per year and per treatment for each crop in the rotation. The treatments are combination of the following factors: CS: cattle slurry; PS: pig slurry; NIT: non-inversion tillage; P: conventional tillage; C0: no compost application; C1: application of 2000 kg C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ plant-based farm compost;

Table 3: Analysis of Variance Table. Response variable: Coefficient of variation

		F	Df	Pr(>F)
Silage maize	Treatment	131.89	7	0.36
	Year	101.61	1	0.02
Potato	Treatment	449.34	7	0.05
	Year	19.19	1	0.41
Spring barley	Treatment	59.13	7	0.72
	Year	70.6	1	0.03
Fodder beet	Treatment	29.68	7	0.82
	Year	1.62	1	0.68

Analysis per factor

Yield

In Figure 7, Figure 9, and Figure 11 the mean annual yield per crop per year for all treatments based on the different experimental factors are shown and in Figure 8, Figure 10, and Figure 12 the mean yield of all treatments of the different experimental factors across the years for each crop are shown.

For silage maize, the ANOVA results indicate that the **year** had a highly significant effect on yield ($p < <0.001$). However, none of the experimental factors—**slurry type** ($p = 0.51$), **tillage** ($p = 0.59$), and **compost dose** ($p = 0.48$)—demonstrated significant differences in yield. Additionally, no significant interactions were observed between factors: **slurry type and tillage** ($p = 0.43$), **slurry type and compost dose** ($p = 0.34$), **tillage and compost dose** ($p = 0.99$), or the three-way interaction of **slurry type, tillage, and compost dose** ($p = 0.87$).

For potato yields, the **year** also showed a significant effect ($p < 0.001$). However, factors such as **slurry type** ($p = 0.13$), **tillage** ($p = 0.56$), and **compost dose** ($p = 0.99$) did not exhibit statistically significant differences in yield. The interaction effects were also non-significant: **slurry type and tillage** ($p = 0.28$), **slurry type and compost dose** ($p = 0.46$), **tillage and compost dose** ($p = 0.62$), and **slurry type, tillage, and compost dose** ($p = 0.59$).

In contrast, for spring barley, the ANOVA results both for **slurry type** ($p < 0.001$) and **tillage** ($p < 0.001$) showed highly significant effects on yield. Nevertheless, the post hoc multiple comparisons test did not indicate statistically significant differences for **tillage method** ($p = 0.1$) and marginally significant differences for the slurry type ($p = 0.049$). Thus, while ANOVA suggests a potential effect, the post hoc analysis indicates that this effect may not be large or consistent enough and confident conclusions cannot be drawn. No significant differences were observed for **compost dose** ($p = 0.50$) or for the interaction effects: **slurry type and tillage** ($p = 0.22$), **slurry type and compost dose** ($p = 0.41$), **tillage and compost dose** ($p = 0.90$), or the three-way interaction ($p = 0.81$). The **year** factor was also statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). As a side note, yield data of 2012 were clearly affected by lodging of the spring barley in summer (Figure 6). This effect was most pronounced in the plots that were ploughed and received pig slurry (PS-P-C0 and PS-P-C1) and resulted in a significantly lower grain dry matter yield in those plots (significant interaction effect slurry type x tillage; $p < 0.05$). This effect was attributed to a higher N-uptake as was shown from the crop quality parameters where the highest N-content of both the grain and the straw of the spring barley was observed in the PS-P plots (significant interaction effect slurry type x tillage; $p < 0.05$). Numerous studies have shown that appropriate nitrogen (N) positively affects barley yield increase, while excessive N decreases stem resistance to lodging and reduces yield.

Figure 6: Lodging of the spring barley on the BOPACT field trial in the summer of 2012

For the fodder beet the **year** exhibited a highly significant effect on yield ($p < 0.001$). Among experimental factors, **slurry type** approached significance ($p = 0.08$), while **compost dose** ($p = 0.14$) and **tillage** ($p = 0.71$) were not statistically significant. The interaction between **slurry type and compost dose** was statistically significant ($p = 0.03$) however the Tukey post-hoc testing did not reveal any statistically significant differences among the factors. Interactions between **slurry type and tillage** ($p = 0.44$), **tillage and compost dose** ($p = 0.13$), and the three-way interaction ($p = 0.55$) were not significant.

The findings indicate that the **year** consistently influences yield across all crops studied, while factor effects vary. The lack of factor effects across the different crops suggests that year-to-year variability may have a more substantial impact on yield than the applied treatments.

Slurry type

Figure 7: Mean annual yield per crop per year for all treatments with pig (PS) or cuttle slurry (CS)

Figure 8: Mean yield of all treatments with pig (PS) or cuttle slurry (CS) across the years for each crop

Tillage method

Figure 9: Mean annual yield per crop per year for all treatments with ploughing (P) or non-inversion tillage (NIT)

Figure 10: Mean yield of all treatments with ploughing (P) or non-inversion tillage (NIT) across the years for each crop

Compost dose

Figure 11: Mean annual yield of all treatments with (C1) or without (C0) compost application per crop and per year

Figure 12: Mean yield of all treatments with (C1) or without (C0) compost application across the years for each crop

Yield stability

In Figure 13, Figure 14, and Figure 15 the CV per crop per year for all treatments based on the different experimental factors are shown.

The ANOVA for the CV in silage maize yields revealed a significant effect of **year** ($p = 0.02$). No significant effects were observed for **slurry type** ($p = 0.35$), **tillage** ($p = 0.68$), or **compost dose** ($p = 0.26$). Interaction effects among the factors were not significant, including **slurry type and tillage** ($p = 0.20$), **slurry type and compost dose** ($p = 0.41$), **tillage and compost dose** ($p = 0.50$), and the three-way interaction ($p = 0.11$).

For potato yields, **slurry type** exhibited a significant effect on CV ($p = 0.01$) with PS to exhibit lower CV. The **compost dose** ($p = 0.63$), **tillage** ($p = 0.10$) and **year** ($p = 0.41$) did not show significant effects. The interactions between **slurry type and tillage** ($p = 0.12$) and **slurry type and compost dose** ($p = 0.26$) were also not significant, along with **tillage and compost dose** ($p = 0.71$) and the three-way interaction ($p = 0.86$).

In spring barley, **year** had a significant effect on CV ($p = 0.04$). However, there were no significant effects from **slurry type** ($p = 0.50$), **tillage** ($p = 0.33$), or **compost dose** ($p = 0.77$). The interactions of **slurry type and tillage** ($p = 0.94$), **slurry type and compost dose** ($p = 0.78$), **tillage and compost dose** ($p = 0.12$), and the three-way interaction ($p = 0.95$) were not significant.

For fodder beet, all factor effects were not significant, with **slurry type** ($p = 0.90$), **tillage** ($p = 0.54$), **compost dose** ($p = 0.34$), and **year** ($p = 0.68$) showing no significant influence on CV. The interactions between **slurry type and tillage** ($p = 0.81$), **slurry type and compost dose** ($p = 0.36$), **tillage and compost dose** ($p = 0.42$), and the three-way interaction ($p = 0.73$) also did not show significant effects.

In summary, the analysis revealed significant effects of **year** on the CV in silage maize ($p = 0.02$) and spring barley ($p = 0.04$), while **slurry type** significantly influenced CV in potatoes ($p = 0.01$). However, no significant effects were observed for fodder beet, nor were there significant interactions among the experimental factors across all crops.

Figure 13: Coefficient of variation (CV) per crop per year for all treatments with pig (PS) or cuttle (CS) slurry

Figure 14: Coefficient of variation (CV) per crop per year for all treatments with ploughing (P) or non-inversion (NIT) tillage

Figure 15: Coefficient of variation (CV) all treatments with (C1) or without (C0) compost application per crop and per year

Climate extremes

As shown in Table 3 for the analysis per treatment and from the results from the analysis per factor, yield stability differs significantly among the years for both silage maize and spring barley.

For silage maize, the flowering and kernel development stages are particularly critical in terms of moisture requirements, occurring primarily in July during the BOPACT field trial. By assessing heat stress and drought stress through degree days and cumulative rainfall, respectively, for the month of July, it was found that 2018 experienced both heat and drought stress, while 2022 was characterized solely by drought, considering the climate data from 1979-2023. Figure 16 illustrates that the CV is higher in years experiencing drought stress compared to normal years. ANOVA analysis indicates that the CV is statistically significantly higher during **drought years** ($p = 0.0005$). However, no significant **effects of the treatments** were detected ($p = 0.161$), nor was there a significant interaction between the years under drought stress and the treatments ($p = 0.30$). No significant effects of the different **factors** (slurry type $p = 0.30$, tillage method $p = 0.64$, compost dose $p = 0.20$) or their interactions were also observed.

Figure 16: Coefficient of variation between years under drought stress (2018, 2022) and normal no-drought years (2010, 2014) for the silage maize

For spring barley, climatic conditions play a crucial role in its growth for an extended period. To assess these conditions, climatic extremes were evaluated for the months of May through July. The years 2012 and 2016 were marked by extreme rainfall conditions, as indicated by cumulative rainfall values in the 90th percentile. Interestingly, the CV was found to be higher during the years with no extreme rainfalls (Figure 17). ANOVA analysis revealed that the CV is statistically significantly higher in non-extreme rainfall years (2012 and 2016) ($p = 0.002$) compared to the normal year of 2023. Furthermore, the interaction between years and extreme rainfall conditions was also significant ($p = 0.03$). However, no significant effect of the treatments ($p = 0.21$) nor the different experimental factors were observed (slurry type $p = 0.47$, tillage method $p = 0.29$, compost dose $p = 0.76$) nor their interactions.

Figure 17: Coefficient of variation between years with extreme rainfall (2012, 2016) and normal year (2023) for spring barley

Discussion and Conclusions

The results from the BOPACT field trial highlight the significant impact of climatic conditions on yield and yield stability. Our analysis revealed statistically significant differences in both yield and yield stability across the years, indicating that external factors such as drought and other climate-related stresses play a crucial role in influencing crop performance. These findings align with existing literature emphasizing the necessity of adapting agricultural practices to cope with changing climate conditions to ensure sustainable yield outcomes.

Interestingly, the treatments and experimental factors applied in this trial did not exhibit statistically significant effects on yield or yield stability. This lack of response suggests that the specific treatments tested do not significantly influence the crops' ability to withstand variability in climate. Furthermore, while certain treatments may enhance yield under optimal conditions, their effectiveness may diminish during periods of stress, such as drought.

In addition to climatic factors, other parameters, particularly soil parameters, may contribute significantly to the observed differences in yield and could explain some inconsistencies in yield stability as soil health influences the nutrient availability, water retention, and overall crop resilience.

Although the yield stability index demonstrated significant differences between years characterized by climatic stress and normal conditions, it is important to note that we only have a few data points for each crop. Consequently, the conclusions drawn at this stage should be regarded as preliminary. Further research with extended duration and additional variables will be necessary to understand if there are effects of treatments, experimental and environmental factors on yield and yield stability.

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